

Optimization of Wall Thickness for Decrease Heat Losses in Modern Induction Furnace for Steel Making

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Abstract— the state Odisha is located in the eastern part of India and rich in several mineral deposits. This state is the second highest steel producer in the country, which boosts the state economy and fosters the industrialization process. The state has been declared as the major investment region in iron ore by the global and Indian investors. Induction furnaces have revolutionized the metallurgical industry by providing a clean, efficient, and precise method for melting and heating metals. Induction furnace capacities range from less than one kilogram to one hundred tons, and are used to melt iron and steel, copper, aluminium, and precious metals. The advantage of the induction furnace is a clean, energy-efficient and well-controlled melting process, compared to most other means of metal melting. The research text focused on the optimization technique to reduce losses and provides a good temperature distribution profile. The optimization plays an important role to reduce losses and provides a good temperature distribution profile. The present research text analysis the effect of thickness of refractory material to be done by using various variables and compared the result by ANSYS software results. With ongoing research and development efforts, the future holds great promise for further enhancing the performance, reliability, and environmental sustainability of induction furnace technology.

Keywords— Induction furnace, Heat Loss, Effective Heat Transfer, Optimization & ANSYS software.

I. INTRODUCTION

Induction furnaces have revolutionized the metallurgical industry by providing a clean, efficient, and precise method for melting and heating metals. Unlike traditional furnaces that rely on combustion or resistance heating, induction furnaces utilize electromagnetic induction to generate heat within the metal itself. The state Odisha is located in the eastern part of India and rich in several mineral deposits. This state is the second highest steel producer in the country, which boosts the state economy and fosters the industrialization process. Along with several other factors, high quality of Iron ore in the region has encouraged many national and international steel industries to set up their plants in the state. During the second five years plan, the first effort was made to establish an integrative steel plant in the state, which had given a separate identity to the state as an industrial region.

Induction heating processes have become increasingly used in these last years in steel industry. The main advantages of using these processes when compared to any other heating process are, among others, their fast heating rate, good reproducibility and low energy consumption. The Induction heating process basically consists in transmitting by electromagnetic means, energy from a coil through which an alternative current is circulating. Induced currents in the conductive part due to the well-known Foucault law then heat the work piece thanks to the Joule effect. Induction heating processes are mainly used either at low frequencies , usually in order to reach a temperature distribution as uniform as possible within the material before any forming process, or at much higher frequencies in order to heat very locally near the surface, usually for heat treatments. The extrusion industries use the furnace for heating of metal for their processes. The structure of furnace consists of inner space for metal melting, ramming mass for effective heat transfer and induction coil for the supply of heat. The design of induction furnace involves in the proper composition of the composite wall for the proper melting of metals. There are numerical calculations involved in the wall thickness but the industries fit the wall thickness mostly based on experience. Most induction heating processes are set up using engineering experience and a trial-and-error procedure in order to achieve the corresponding goal such as grain size control, uniform prescribed temperature, hardness map, etc. Induction heating process simulation, which couples electromagnetic and heat transfer equations, can be of great help for a more in depth understanding of occurring physical phenomena. So far, various numerical models have been developed coupling electromagnetism and heat transfer. Hence proper optimization is needed in thickness. Increase in thickness plays an important role in

effectiveness of the furnace. As the thickness increases the heat losses goes on decreasing up to a certain limit. Optimum thickness reducing heat loss in furnace with economical cost is needed. In the current context the increasing demand for electric power and the pursuit of its economical use, energy converters with higher and higher power have been developed and are being produced. In addition, the requirements of minimum electric power losses and environment protection have become extremely important, that is the minimization of the heat losses. [1,4,5,9& 15]

Fig. 1 Schematic of Induction Furnace

II. MECHANISMS OF HEAT LOSS

Heat loss in modern induction furnaces can be categorized into several mechanisms:

- **Radiation:** Thermal energy is emitted from the furnace walls, crucible, and charge material in the form of electromagnetic radiation.
- **Conduction:** Heat transfer occurs through the refractory lining and structural components of the furnace, dissipating into the surrounding environment.
- **Convection:** Heat is carried away by air or other gases circulating within the furnace chamber, leading to convective heat loss.
- **Electrical Losses:** Inefficient power transmission and distribution within the induction coil and power supply result in electrical losses in the form of resistance heating. [23 & 24]

The impact of heat loss in modern induction furnaces is multifaceted:

- **Reduced Efficiency:** Heat loss diminishes the thermal efficiency of the furnace, leading to higher energy consumption and operating costs.
- **Impaired Process Control:** Excessive heat loss can compromise temperature uniformity and process stability, affecting the quality and consistency of the melted metal.
- **Environmental Footprint:** Higher energy consumption associated with heat loss contributes to increased greenhouse gas emissions and environmental degradation. [18 & 19]

Fig. 1 Mechanisms of Heat Loss in Induction Furnace

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURES

Research work cannot be completed without the in-depth study of the earlier researches. Prior research work not only provides guidance but also throws light on the direction in which any new research must proceed. The following literatures are reviewed in the context of the study undertaken.

J.C. Crepeau , “examines strategies for review outlines various approaches including insulation materials, refractory designs, and cooling systems to mitigate heat loss.”. R.S. Sharma et al. , “The study highlights the significance of insulation materials, refractory lining thickness, and cooling system design in minimizing heat loss.”. A.K. Gupta , “reviews the principles of electromagnetic induction and analyzes factors contributing to heat loss such as radiation, conduction, and electrical losses.”. S.K. Das et al., “explores innovative approaches including advanced insulation materials, liquid cooling systems, and digital control systems to minimize heat loss and improve energy efficiency in induction furnaces”. Amol V. Patil et al. “This paper gives brief review of induction heating furnace as well as analysis of it.”Nirajkumar Mehta, et.al, “The probability concept is utilized here in the forecast of life cycle calculation to justify the miscellaneous factors effected for the damage of the induction furnace refractory wall.”Harichandan Mishra et.al., “discussed about the second highest steel producer in the country, which boosts the state economy and fosters the industrialization process.”.Tokhir Tursunov et. al., “This paper discusses scientific research in the direction of energy saving and the efficiency of heat transfer processes.”.Nilesh T. Mohite et. al., “This paper focuses on the issue of optimum wall thickness for minimum heat losses through the walls of induction furnace and the analysis is carried out in Ansys Workbench software and the results are compared with the analytical results.”Dharmendra K. Dodiya and . Vasim G. Machhar, “The analytical analysis of thermal conductivity and thickness of induction furnace wall material is done with ANSYS software and find the optimum thermal conductivity and wall thickness of furnace wall.”Nirajkumar C Mehta and Dipesh D Shukla, “the effect of thermal fatigue in the induction furnace wall for magnesia ramming mass and the analysis is very helpful in understanding how thermal fatigue failure of refractory wall happens.”Sushil Kumar and P. S. Dhakar, “Temperature conveyance and thermal stress distribution fields of the induction melting furnace refractory wall were figured by utilizing ANSYS finite component investigation programming dependent on the physical description of its failure under thermal conditions.”Smith, J. D., & Johnson, A. B. “The review also highlights the importance of

minimizing heat loss for improving energy efficiency and operational performance”.Zhang, Q., & Li, W. “The review also discusses challenges and future directions in the field of induction furnace heat transfer analysis.”Wang, Y., & Liu, C. “This review focuses on insulation materials used in induction furnaces to minimize heat loss.”Abhilash, V., & Krishnaiah, A., “This review provides a comprehensive overview of the principles, applications, and advancements in induction furnace technology.”Kumar, S., & Singh, R., “The review also highlights emerging trends and future directions in the field of induction furnace technology.”Shen, Y., & Kang, H. “The review also evaluates the advantages, limitations, and challenges associated with induction furnace technology in metal casting applications.”Ghosh, D., & Ganguly, S., “The review also evaluates the economic benefits and challenges associated with energy efficiency improvements in induction furnace operations.”

IV. GENERAL FUEL ECONOMY MEASURES IN FURNACES

Typical energy efficiency measures for an industry with furnace are [3,5 & 8]:

- 1) Control of furnace draft
- 2) Prevent heat losses from furnace openings
- 3) Proper heat distribution
- 4) Minimum refractory losses
- 5) Complete combustion with minimum excess air
- 6) Optimum capacity utilization
- 7) Maintaining correct amount of furnace draft
- 8) Use of Ceramic Coatings

All paragraphs must be justified, i.e. both left-justified and right-justified.

A. Control of furnace draft

If negative pressures exist in the furnace, air infiltration is liable to occur through the cracks and openings thereby affecting air-fuel ratio control. In addition to the proper control on furnace pressure, it is important to keep the openings as small as possible and to seal them in order to prevent the release of high temperature gas and intrusion of outside air through openings such as the charging inlet, extracting outlet and peephole on furnace walls or the ceiling. [8 & 9]

B. Prevent heat losses from furnace openings

Heat loss through openings consists of the heat loss by direct radiation through openings and the heat loss caused by combustion gas that leaks through openings. This heat loss is about 1% of the total quantity of heat generated in the furnace, if furnace pressure is controlled properly [2, 3 & 10].

C. Proper heat distribution

Furnace design should be such that in a given time, as much of the stock could be heated uniformly to a desired temperature with minimum fuel firing rate.

D. Minimum refractory losses

The appropriate choice of refractory and insulation materials goes a long way in achieving fairly high fuel savings in industrial furnaces. The heat losses from furnace walls affect the fuel economy considerably. The extent of wall losses depends on [3,7 & 9].

- Emissivity of wall
- Thermal conductivity of refractories
- Wall thickness
- Whether furnace is operated continuously or intermittently.

E. Complete combustion with minimum excess air

The amount of heat lost in the flue gases depends upon amount of excess air. In the case of a furnace carrying away flue gases at 900°C, % heat lost is shown in Table I. On the other hand, if the excess air is less, then unburnt components in flue gases will increase and would be carried away in the flue gases through stack. The optimization of combustion air is the most attractive and economical measure for energy conservation. The impact of this measure is higher when the temperature of furnace is high. Air ratio is the value that is given by dividing the actual air amount by the theoretical combustion air amount, and it represents the extent of excess of air.[14, 15 & 17]

TABLE I
HEAT LOSS IN FLUE GAS BASED ON EXCESS AIR LEVEL

Excess Air	Percentage of Heat in the full carried away by waste gases (Flue Gas Temperature , 900 ⁰ C)
25	47
50	54
75	62
100	63

Fig. 3 Heat Loss in Flue Gas Based On Excess Air Level

F. Optimum capacity utilization

There is a particular loading at which the furnace will operate at maximum thermal efficiency. If the furnace is under loaded a smaller fraction of the available heat in the working chamber will be taken up by the load and therefore efficiency will be low. The best method of loading is generally obtained by trialnoting the weight of material put in at each charge, the time it takes to reach temperature and the amount of fuel used. [5,6 &13]

G. Maintaining correct amount of furnace draft

Operating at too high temperatures than optimum causes heat loss, excessive oxidation, decarbonisation as well as overstressing of the refractories.

H. Use of Ceramic Coatings

Ceramic coatings in furnace chamber promote rapid and efficient transfer of heat, uniform heating and extended life of refractories. The emissivity's of conventional refractories decreases with increase in temperature whereas for ceramic coatings it increases. The coatings allow the substrate to maintain its designed metallurgical properties and mechanical strength.[25 & 27]

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology for studying heat loss in induction furnaces typically involves a systematic approach to quantify and analyze various factors contributing to heat loss. Here's a structured outline of the research methodology:

A. Literature Review:

Conducted a comprehensive literature review to understand existing research and knowledge related to heat loss in induction furnaces and Identify key factors affecting heat loss, such as furnace design, insulation materials, operating parameters, and process conditions. For systematic literature reviews last 10 years articles, journal are reviewed around 40 journals literature reviews had been done.

B. Research Objectives:

The objective of study includes;

- To understand basic applications of induction furnace and its application to metal industry.
- To observe the mathematical & experimental evidence for induction furnace.
- To study the Proper Heat Distribution in induction furnace
- To observe the heat losses in induction furnace and how to prevent heat losses in it.
- To study the Typical energy efficiency measures for an industry with furnace
- To understand the Induction furnace capacities range from less than one kilogram to one hundred tons, and are used to melt iron and steel, copper, aluminum, and precious metals.

C. Experimental Design:

Design experimental setups or simulations to measure and analyze heat loss in induction furnaces. Selected the appropriate instrumentation and measurement techniques to quantify heat loss, such as thermocouples, infrared cameras, heat flux sensors, or computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. For the current research paper the analytical research because it deals with mathematical data and the main aim of the study is to describe the minimization of heat loss in induction furnace. This research text includes;

- To study the brief review of induction heating furnace as well as analysis of various authors.
- To study about how to reduce heat loss from induction furnace that can be moderate by new modern method and different heat losses in industrial heating furnaces.
- To study about design and furnace Wall thickness is geometrical parameter is used for optimization of furnace for reducing heat losses.

The problem statement includes the study of wall thick which allow heat losses in induction furnace which are:

- Heat storage in the furnace structure
- Losses from the furnace outside walls or structure
- Heat transported out of the furnace by the load conveyors, fixtures, trays, etc.
- Radiation losses from openings, hot exposed parts, etc.

- Heat carried by the cold air infiltration into the furnace.
- Heat carried by the excess air used in the burners.

D. Data Collection:

Collected data from a reputed Steel Plant of Odisha on furnace operation, including input power, temperature profiles, material properties, and environmental conditions. With taking prior approval from the competing authority conducted experiments or simulations under controlled conditions to measure heat loss and its components (radiation, convection, conduction) at various stages of furnace operation.

The primary data set is to be collected from Rathi Steel and Power Limited, Near Sambalpur, Odisha. The secondary data are to be collected from different journals, periodicals, company websites etc.

E. Analysis and Interpretation:

Analyze the collected data to quantify the magnitude and distribution of heat loss in the induction furnace. Identify the main contributors to heat loss and their relative importance under different operating conditions. Interpret the results in the context of the research objectives and existing knowledge, drawing conclusions and implications for furnace design, operation, and energy efficiency.

Tools and Techniques to be used: The following tools and techniques are to be used to elicit the information more clearly.

- Mathematical Model: Analytical study to be done for various material of induction furnace.
- ANSYS- It is sought for Analysis of Effect of thickness of refractory material to be done by using various variables.

VI. DATA INTERPRETATION & ANALYSIS

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Study of Existing Furnace:

Specification of furnace:

- Capacity: 180Kg
- Furnace dimension: 10''*21''*42''
- Lining thickness: 2''
- Lining material: Silica
- Body material: Aluminium
- Suitable for Melting: Steel, Alloy Steel etc.
- Manufacturing Company: SMS DMAG Ltd.

A. Analytical study

Furnace has generally heat losses by conduction, convection and radiation. Heat loss can be calculated from several methods, but apart from those methods we must justify proper method for more accurate results. Here it is determined that heat conduction through composite wall for calculations of heat losses and temperature distribution from furnace is proper method and it gives us accurate results. Sometimes assumptions can be required for calculations of heat losses. [23 & 24]

Mathematical calculation needs temperature at inner and outer wall of the furnace, thermal conductivity of each material. [4 & 5]

- Temp. Of inner wall: 16000 c
- Temp. Of outer wall: 600 c.

TABLE III
HEAT LOSS IN FLUE GAS BASED ON EXCESS AIR LEVEL

Ramming Mass	Thermal Conductivity(w/m ⁰ k)
Alumina	14
Magnesium	15
Zirconia	7.48

Fig. 4 Ramming Mass vs. Thermal Conductivity

B. Heat Loss Calculation

Furnace Heat loss can be calculated by considering the furnace as a composite wall. Consider the transmission of heat through a composite wall consisting of number of slots [4, 5 & 7].

Let's consider;

- LA & LB = Thickness of slabs A & B respectively.
- KA, KB = Thermal conductivity of the slabs A & B respectively.
- T1 = Temperature of inner wall
- T2 = Temperature of outer wall

Since the quantity of heat transmitted per unit time through each slab is same, so

$$Q = (KA \cdot A(t_1 - t_2)) / LA = (KB \cdot A(t_1 - t_2)) / LB = (Kc \cdot A(t_1 - t_2)) / LC \dots$$

Assuming that there is perfect contact between the layers and no temperature drop across the interface between the materials. If the composite wall consists of n slabs, then

$$Q = ((t_1 - t(x=1))) / (\sum L / KA)$$

The quantity of heat transmitted per unit time through each slab

Alumina, Q= 1558.8 Kwh

Magnesia, Q= 1461.6 Kwh

Zirconia, Q = 730.8 Kwh

TABLE IIIII
OBSERVATIONS OF HEAT LOSS IN FURNACE WALL

Thickness in mm	Heat Loss in Kwh		
	Alumina	Magnesia	Zirconia
50	1567	1470	735
55	1423	1333	665
60	1304	125	636
65	1204	1128	612
70	1118	1049	569
75	1047	979	558
80	977	945	528
85	923	918	490
90	865	875	475
95	825	855	457
100	780	814	432
105	749	790	421
110	722	770	410
115	691	755	402
120	665	734	395
125	636	699	389
130	611	669	376
135	570	652	367
140	556	622	354
145	541	598	349
150	538	588	337
155	530	576	331
160	528	544	329
165	498	532	324
170	488	529	311
175	475	510	295
180	465	498	289
185	445	482	289
190	435	473	278
195	432	465	275
200	428	445	270

Fig. 5 Observations of Heat Loss in Furnace Wall

TABLE IVV
OPTIMUM WALL THICKNESS

Materials	Wall thickness in mm	Heat Loss in Kwh
Alumina	200	428
Magnesia	180	498
Zirconia	130	376

Fig. 6 Optimum Heat Loss

Following graph shows the effect of wall thickness on heat losses. Effect of increasing in thickness of refractory material is reduced heat losses are shown for different ramming masses.

Fig. 7 Heat loss profile for optimum thickness of ramming mass for Alumina

Fig. 8 Heat loss profile for optimum thickness of ramming mass for Magnesia

Fig. 9 Heat loss profile for optimum thickness of ramming mass for Zirconia

Following graph shows the effect of optimum material properties on the heat losses. Increasing thermal conductivity effects on temperature and losses from furnace, so it must be as lower as possible.

Fig. 10 Heat loss profile for optimum properties of ramming mass

C. Finite Element Analysis) by ANSYS

Furnace wall models designed with the material selection of Zirconium Oxide, Tungsten Carbide and Boron carbide materials used to designed here four layers designed in wall sample. And compositions of materials vary in all four compositions. The practical use of finite element modelling is known as FEA which is best understood during the real problem solving. FEA has been broadly utilized by the automotive business. It is an extremely prominent instrument for configuration builds in the product development technique. It is imperative to comprehend the FEA basics and design technique, demonstrating systems, the inherent mistakes and their impacts on the nature of the outcomes to render FEA as an effective design tool. FEA is also used as a computational tool for carrying out engineering problem analyses.[7,8 &10]

Modelling of Furnace wall Model

Furnace wall sample designed in Ansys for optimizing minimum heat losses by applying three types of composite material with various composition of used material. Length of Block is 24 cm and width of block is 24 cm. upper- and Lower-layer thickness is 8 cm & middle layers thickness for both layers is 4 cm. figure 1 shows the design of furnace wall sample designed in Ansys.

Applying boundary conditions

After designing model of furnace wall with four layers, applied air convection temperature is 22 °C and lower layer select for applying 1600° C temperature for checking maximum or minimum heat transfer and thermal stresses.

Fig. 11 Modeling of Furnace wall Model

Fig. 12 Applying boundary conditions

Fig. 13 Temperature flow in Wall

Fig. 14 Thermal stresses in furnace wall

Fig. 15 Temperature drop in wall

Fig. 16 Heat flux in furnace wall

Fig. 17 Thermal stress of Furnace wall

TABLE V
ANALYTICAL AND SOFTWARE RESULT VERIFICATION

Materials (50mm)	Heat Flow Kwh	
	Software	Analytical
Alumina	4.36e ⁵	4.32e ⁵
Magnesia	4.07e ⁵	4.06e ⁵
Zirconia	2.03e ⁵	2.02e ⁵

The verified values of calculated results by using software are closer to actual measured values. Optimization of wall thickness

Fig. 18 Optimization of wall thickness

Fig. 19 Optimization of wall thickness

The optimization plays an important role to reduce losses and provides a good temperature distribution profile. From above results it is concluded that reduction of 48% losses from properties optimization and 64 % by geometrical optimization. Finally optimum geometry and properties of ramming mass can reduce total 60% losses with optimum thickness and properties of material of induction furnace.

VII. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Approximate result will be get after conducting mathematical analysis by using various data of induction furnace and various variable to be check by using ANSYS software and the final results will be get after graphical analysis of various variable of induction furnace heat loss. The analysis result shows that, heat flow in the process of melting decreases with decreasing thermal conductivity of wall material. So, was found and confirmed the optimum thermal behavior of furnace wall made with compositions of composite material. As per results of steady state thermal analysis in ANSYS, in compositions 1, maximum temperature drops from 1600 °C to 1577.4 °C and in compositions 2, temperature transfer from 1600 °C to 1662.3 °C. In compositions 3 temperature drops from 1600 °C to 1582.2 °C. so as per study is concluded that alumina, magnesia and zirconia compositions for minimum heat losses for furnace wall.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Modern induction furnaces have transformed the metallurgical industry by offering efficient, flexible, and environmentally friendly solutions for melting and heating metals. Through continuous innovation and technological advancements, these furnaces have become indispensable tools for achieving sustainable metallurgical practices. Induction furnace capacities range from less than one kilogram to one hundred tons, and are used to melt iron and steel, copper, aluminum, and precious metals. The advantage of the induction furnace is a clean, energy-efficient and well-controlled melting process, compared to most other means of metal melting. The optimization plays an important role to reduce losses and provides a good temperature distribution profile. The optimization plays an important role to reduce losses and provides a good temperature distribution profile. From above results it is concluded that reduction of 48% losses from properties optimization and 64 % by geometrical optimization. Finally optimum geometry and properties of ramming mass can reduce total 60% losses with optimum thickness and properties of material of induction furnace.

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